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Appraising Intellectual Capital and Effective Banking Industry Management in Nigeria

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Abstract:

This article appraised the probable effects of Intellectual Capital on effective Banking Industry Management in Nigeria. Intellectual Capital proxies' namely: Human capital, Structural capital and Relationship capital were engaged in formulating three null hypotheses that were estimated and analyzed to explain effective Banking industry management. The study adopted Survey research design and data were assembled through questionnaire administration and estimated utilizing Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC) denoted by 'r'. The results were robust as the PPMCC or 'r' coefficients for H₀₁ that explored Human Capital and effective Banking management exhibited extreme high value of 0.8762 suggesting that the variable is significant. Its corresponding (r²) coefficient stood at 0.7677 indicating that the model has high predictive power. The values of 'r' and (r²) coefficients of H₀₂ that evaluated Structural capital were equally high though H₀₃ that appraised Relationship capital exhibited somewhat moderate to high values of 'r' and (r²) coefficients. Overall, the results led us to conclude that Intellectual capital is an essential prerequisite for effective banking industry management and could be counted relevant to formulating policies to augment effective management of banks. We therefore recommend that banks should invest immensely on Human, Structural and Relationship capital programs to improve and sustain effective banking industry management

Keywords: Intellectual capital, Human capital, Structural capital, Relationship capital, Banking management, Nigeria.

American Economic Association JEL Classification: G1, G2, G4

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In modern organizations, intangible intellectual assets and knowledge-based resources are now being considered in terms of wealth creation as more dominant assets than tangible assets such as plants, land, cast, et cetera. The concept of Intellectual Capital (IC) is therefore becoming a major focus amongst leading corporation's management teams desiring effectiveness and sustainable success in creating wealth. Basically, IC denotes knowledge-based, intangible and unapparent assets and resources that allows organizations to innovate, generate value and gain competitive edge over others. Chen (2021) averred that Intellectual capital has to do with the knowledge, business ideas, skills, information resources, et cetera at an organization's disposal that makes it have competitive advantage, gain customers and improve the company's ability to drive profits. This definition is all embracing as it spans employees' expertise to information and data possessed by the company in their systems used for wealth creation. From the foregoing, Intellectual capital is therefore seen as viable business assets that can facilitate organizational processes, the expertise possess by employees and the totality of knowledge, skills held within the company or organization. Adegbayibi (2021) affirmed that Intellectual

capacity is important to achieving effective management of resources, attaining high level of company performance and ultimately in gaining competitive edge.

In the views of Marr, Schiuma and Neely, (2004), the transformation of business processes to digital economy has helped to bring to fore the idea and theory of Intellectual Capital and is now being adopted in measuring organization's performance. Emphasis is now given to the usefulness and practicability of Intellectual Capital as it assists companies to optimally and flawlessly utilize their human resources as critical factor in achieving competitive edge and actualizing organization's set goals. Adegbayibi (2021) pointed out that the need for investing and developing Intellectual Capital became necessary because of changing trends in the world economy as per constant changes in production processes, innovations in service delivery, world economic crisis, and development in knowledge-based organizations in particular. Globally and especially in Nigeria competition has intensified amongst local, international and multinational businesses and corporations. ExxonMobil (2014) report stated that to meet with competition and build up their Intellectual Capital, Unilever Plc's invested over N40m in 2008 in the training of employees and Exxon spent \$117m in 2014 in preparing its workforce to retain strategic competitive edge in the industry. Businesses have also made efforts to raise and augment their Intellectual Capital by engaging qualified employees, developing and evolving new franchise or patents. Knowledge-based organizations spend quality time and huge resources developing management expertise, training and re-training their employees in business-specific areas to increase their mental capacity, in other words, to increase their enterprise capabilities.

Effective management in every organization relates to planning, controlling and organizing the entire firm or corporation's resources to drive its goals and objectives. Specifically, effective banking industry management revolves round a combination of strategic planning, operational efficiency, risk management and customer-centric approach. In this age of digitalization buildup and expansion cum globalization, trends in organizations and indeed banking firms must be effectively managed to harness and exploit technological investments in productive systems. The modern views in industries believe that effective management performance can reach its goal by developing Intellectual Capital; otherwise there could be deep decline in organization's abilities and financial performance as it relates specifically to banking institutions. Duho and Agomor (2021) argued that firms lacking in Intellectual Capital labour so hard to sustain their productive capabilities and that results in dwindling micro and macro variables in the economy generally. The need for effective management of resources in the economy generally and in the banking industry in particular has thus become serious issues requiring urgent handling. It is on this ground that Habib (2018) strongly advocates that corporations and indeed the banking sector firms need to develop strong and innovative strategies and business models around Intellectual Capital to excel and take advantage of the huge economic resources in Nigeria and Africa. The ever growing complexities of businesses, corporate entities and organization demand diverse strategies to facilitate and enhance management capabilities and effectiveness in service delivery so as to maintain and sustain productivity.

Aguirre and Alecchi (2023), affirmed strongly that sustainable growth and advancement will be lacking in our industries without developing and improving Intellectual Capital efficiently. Intellectual capital possesses some fundamental components which could be categorized into three groups, namely: Human capital, Structural capital and Relationship capital.

- **Human capital:** This consists of the knowledge, expertise, experience and skills of the employees in a company or an organization. It takes into account their education, work and life experiences and on-the-job training. Training and re-training of employees increase, boost and buildup the Human capital of a firm.
- **Structural capital:** This refers to the firm such as the banking institution's core processes, systems and infrastructures that support and aid the development of knowledge, sharing of knowledge and

utilization of knowledge. It includes policies of the company, mission and vision statements, the company's structure and work culture.

- **Relationship capital:** It encompasses networks, partnership and the associations that the company has with stakeholder, employees, partners, suppliers, shareholder, customers, et cetera.

These components, Human capital, Structural capital and Relationship capital are used as proxies for Intellectual Capital and constitute the explanatory variables to explain effective Banking Industry Management serving as the dependent or explained variable in this study. Based on the underlying discussions we specify the research objective. The main objective is to determine the inter-relationship existing between the concept and notion of Intellectual Capital and effective Banking industry management. The specific objectives attempt to investigate how each of the explanatory variables, namely: Human Capital, Structural Capital and Relationship Capital affect effective Banking industry management. Therefore, we formulated hypothesis for each of the independent or explanatory variables with respect to management of banking institutions.

1.1 Hypotheses Formulation.

Three null hypotheses are drawn from the objectives of study to be tested and from where reasonable inferences and conclusions will be drawn. These include:

H₀₁ Human Capital has no significant and compelling effects on effective Banking industry Management

H₀₂ Structural Capital has no significant relationship with effective Banking industry Management.

H₀₃ Relationship Capital has no significant influence on effective Banking industry Management

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURES

The obvious fact in the business world today is that competition has become very intense amongst modern businesses, so the ability of management teams of corporations have been brought under serious focus. The need to make banking institutions perform maximally after decades of financial crisis, liquidations and distresses makes it of utmost importance. Intellectual capital (IC) is known today as a knowledge-based assets that allows corporations focus on how efficiency and effectiveness of management team cum financial performance could be advanced. By definition, Intellectual Capital represents intellectual property, knowledge, skills and experience possessed by a corporation that can be employed to add value to the corporation resources and create wealth. In accordance to Payam & Mohammad, (2013), it describes and represents a collective knowledge of the employees in the corporation, organization, banking institution and even the individuals in the society. Scholarly literatures suggest that Intellectual Capital is a nexus, a kind of mediator subsisting between effective management and the firm's efficient performance. Hanady, Sinan, Enas and Amneh (2022), investigated IC on the performance of various types of businesses and how management role could be effective in this context. The results signified that the corporation's ability to effectively utilize its IC contributed more to success in raising its market value and generally, its financial performance. Nasar (2018) argues that Intellectual Capital is very crucial for creating and adding value in an economic era where there is intensive competition amongst organizations, businesses and industries. The reason is not farfetched, present corporations, economies and indeed corporations are knowledge-based and are driven with highly sophisticated intrinsic assets residing in the heads of their employees to build competitive edge.

With the advent of Financial Technologies (FinTech), banking institutions employees need increased Intellectual Capital in its entire ramifications to meet competition in the industry. This explains reasons why several banking firms must keep enhancing the skills, talent, expertise and proficiency of their employees through training, re-training, conducting researches and investing in customer relations. So, developing Intellectual Capital must be the initiative of management because how management perceives IC will decide the degree of motivation employees will receive. Adegbayibi (2021) reported that management has the role to bring in skilled and knowledgeable employees that bring to bear improvements, advancement, enhancement and innovations that will attract customers and appeal to their initiative to pay for services and products. It is therefore imperative for management of organizations and particularly banking institutions to consistently improve corporate knowledge, skills, expertise and capabilities so as to create value and wealth efficiently. The reasoning is that it is the way managers and employees accomplish their job tasks that will determine the level

of performance and accomplishment of the bank or organization. Yusoff and Alhaji, (2012) posits that Management consisting of Board of Directors are stewards and stewardship theory with respect to Intellectual Capital focuses on the effectiveness of the executives.

Human capital is the blend and combination of intrinsic endowment or values such as knowledge, skill, education, experiences and attitude of employees that the organizations use to produce superior products, fashion or model a trademark for themselves and gain competitive edge. Management coordinates these impalpable assets and values to achieve best results for the organization. Banyai, Landschuter and Banyai (2018) opined that Human capital efficiency depends on management ability to effectively optimize the organization or bank knowledge, skills and expertise of its employees to achieve and sustain corporate objectives. Human capital efficiency starts from quality engagement or recruitment of employees. It denotes proper placement, productive allocation and efficient delegation of duties to employees. In the banking industry, effective management of Human capital is necessary and important for driving business growth, improving customer satisfaction and maintaining a competitive advantage. There are core elements and ingredients of Human Capital that banking professionals need. They require specialized knowledge and skills which include financial analysis, regulatory compliance and risk management. Bankers need expertise in specific areas such as investment banking, or retail banking which constitutes valuable assets. Effective Management and indeed Managers are essential for guiding teams, making strategic decisions and driving business results. Adaptability and innovation are also key areas of Human capital because banking professional should be able to adapt to changing market conditions, regulatory requirements and technological advancement. Thus, effective Human capital management in banking includes talent acquisition and development, performance management, succession planning, diversity equity and inclusion, employee engagement, et cetera. Becker (2001) summed it up that the best successful and prosperous companies and countries are those that control Human capital in the most effective and efficient fashion – investing in their workers, helping employees to invest and improve their abilities, providing good learning environment, and yes, including social or relationship capital and indeed skills and training.

Structural capital is another core area of Intellectual Capital and it implies the corporation's infrastructures, systems and processes that buttress and support the utilization of the philosophy, knowledge, ability and expertise within an organization to create shareholder value. It plays very relevant role in enhancing the organization's processes and infrastructures in wealth creation. Structural capital efficiency involves managing and controlling the data base of a company, specifically, a bank to operate effectively. Pursuant to Chaabane (2021), Structural capital provides support to non-physical corporate infrastructures of the organization to leverage employees' ability to function efficiently. Taking the form of managerial procedure, it connotes a serious link which allows Intellectual Capital to be dignified and elevated. In banking sector, effective, adept and profitable management of structural capital is important for boosting business growth, improving operational efficiency and preserving and sustaining competitive edge. VanZyl (2005), affirmed that Structural Capital Management creates sustainable competitiveness, supports innovation, assist in better risk management, aids compliance with regulatory requirements and supports enhanced customer experience. Major constituents or rather, integral parts of Structural Capital in Banking include: Information Technology (IT) systems to support banking operations, customer service delivery and risk management; Knowledge management system to capture, store and share knowledge, Process and procedures standardization and Physical infrastructures and intellectual property, the likes of patents, trademarks, copyright, et cetera.

Ultimately, Relationship capital refers to the value derived from long term, strong and healthy relationships that organizations such as banks maintain with their customers, stakeholders, partners and employees. It relates to the amiable and cordial relationship that a corporation uphold with employees, shareholders and internal stakeholders, the employees and external stakeholders including suppliers, shareholders, et cetera. In consonance with VanZyl (2005), Relationship capital is a vital and necessary component and segment of Intellectual capital that corporations acquire to attain sustainable competitiveness. It helps to solidify customer preferences, integrate and consolidate suppliers' interest with increased loyalty. However, VanZyl (2005),

further suggests that Relationship capital does need to be supported with Structural capital for an organization to add value and sustain the benefits Intellectual capital seeks to achieve. Relationship capital is also referred to Social or Rational capital and Buallay (2017) defined it as the corporation's relationship with the external and internal stakeholders who have supreme and vested interest in the affairs of the corporation. Effective management teams employ Relationship capital strategies to efficiently coordinate and relate with the firm's stakeholders. This helps to ensure customer satisfaction, develop employee career needs, boost supplier relations, improve employee benefits, give consideration for regulatory compliances and maintain good relationship with government and industry affiliations. Habib (2018) explained that displaying and demonstrating winning attitude and cordial relationship with all stakeholders in organizations and especially in institutions operating in the banking industry is an asset that effective management can utilize to significantly increase financial standing and performance.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODS

We present hereunder the empirical methods, techniques and procedures made use of in accomplishing and executing the research study.

3.1 Research Design, Population and Sample size

Survey design is believed to be a very dexterous, skillful and comprehensive technique for sourcing for research data. The design is conducted through observations and practical experiences to provide detailed knowledge and accurate state of the population. Creswell (2005), described research population as the most extensive level in which a group of objects, persons or things being studied display common characteristic to distinguish themselves distinctively from other groups. This research topic is intended to put forward an analysis on how Intellectual capital relates to effective banking industry management. Thus, the population focuses on all management employees engaged in Banking Service Providers (BSPs) in Nigeria. However, considering the complexity and enormous size of the population, a Sample population was studied. In conformity with Creswell (2005), a Sample population is described as a selected geographical location where the real list of sampling units exist and from where research data are elicited. Therefore, the Sample population is made up of all Management employees of all BSPs located in Delta and Edo States of Nigeria. With the rule of thumb, a Sample size of seven hundred (700) Management employees were selected and engaged in executing the study.

3.2 Sampling method and Questionnaire model

The 'Random Sampling' technique was applied in the sampling exercise which involved the random distribution of questionnaires. Researchers usually put to use this method because of its fairness and it is seen to be free from biases. It follows established rules in the gathering of study data engaging analytical designed questionnaires. The questionnaire was formatted or patterned into two sections designated 'Demographic section' and 'Question and Answer options section'. The demographic field helps respondents to provide personal information about their status. The Question and Answer section of the analytical questionnaire is structured to conform to an innovation known as 'Item-Specific-Response-Options (ISRO). In line with Wronski (2018), 'Item specific' denotes that the response options are distinct and limited to a peculiar survey question and different questions could be designed to have different group or bundle of response options. This is aimed to aid a respondent to provide a more cohesive response answer to the question given. The ISRO strategy has five points rating scale of answer options. That means that the answer options are ranged starting from Very Affirmative; Somewhat Affirmative; Neutral; Somewhat Negative to Very Negative. These options carry descending weights from 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 attached to Very affirmative to Very negative respectively.

3.3 Data analysis tool, Theoretical framework and Model specification.

The analytical tool engaged in estimating the research data is known as the Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC) represented by alphabet 'r'. PPMCC, also known as Sample coefficient is a reliable statistical tool for measuring the correlation subsisting between variables having undeviating or linear inter-relationship. The coefficient or 'r' signifies the direction, path or bearing and the strength or stability of

inter-relationship prevailing amongst the variable. Sauro (2011) affirmed that a rating scale having five points such as the ISRO scale and weighted from 5 to 1 for Very affirmative to Very negative options respectively can be put forward to determine the value of PPMCC or ‘r’. While computing the ‘r’ value with data obtained from field survey, the Score column represented by X utilizes the Weights attached to answer options and the Nominal column accredited Y relates to respondents answer option frequencies. Boone and Boone (2012), affirmed the suitability of ISRO five point rating scale in computing the value of PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient. We specify below the PPMCC model employed to run the empirical estimation and computation of the value and worth of the ‘r’ coefficient making use of the Weights (X) and the Answer options frequencies (Y). Obadan, (2012), provides a quantitative Model in equation 1 that uses absolute values of data obtained for the computation of PPMCC or ‘r’ value. Equation (1) therefore provides the model as follows:

$$\text{PPMCC or 'r'} = \frac{\sum (X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum (X - \bar{X})^2 \sum (Y - \bar{Y})^2}} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

- Where: ‘r’ = The value of PPMCC existing between the variables
- X = Weighted answer response options
- Y = Frequency of answer response options
- ∑ = Summation sign
- \bar{X} = Mean of weighted response options
- \bar{Y} = Mean of frequency of response options

Experiences from researchers have revealed that manipulating equation 1 in its mathematical form is tedious owing to its complexity. To ease the task of managing equation 1, Obadan, (2012), came forward with a less difficult formula that utilizes the deviations of the variables from their Means. Formula 2 is manipulated applying the deviations ‘x’ and ‘y’ strategy, meaning the deviation of X and Y variables from their respective Means to derive PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient. Model 2 is exhibited in equation (2) as follows:

$$‘r’ = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

- Where: x = X - \bar{X} and
- y = Y - \bar{Y}

3.4 Decision rule:

The rules guide the researcher’s decision in making logical inferences based on the size of the computed value of ‘r’ coefficient. Obadan (2012), asserts that the computed product of PPMCC or ‘r’ usually falls within the realm of -1 to +1. It is such that when:

- ‘r’ value is zero (0), implies that relationship does not exists amongst the variables being reviewed.
- ‘r’ value stands at +1, it means a perfect positive correlation exists and the closer it is to +1, the more ardent and intense the relationship.
- ‘r’ value indicates -1, it signifies that a perfect negative correlation exists and the closer it is to -1, the weaker the relationship.

Another parameter is derived from the value of ‘r’ when squared. It is referred to as ‘Coefficient of Determination (r²)’. The two parameters will be brought to bear in the discussion of findings to explain the relationship subsisting between Intellectual capacity and effective banking industry management.

4.0 PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

As earlier mentioned, 700 questionnaires were randomly administered and 675 of them were retrieved to constitute 96.43% of total distribution. This section presents the response frequencies elicited from respondents for each hypothesis question.

4.1 Presentation of Data for H0₁:

Hypothesis One (H0₁) investigated the Human capital component of Intellectual capital and how it relates with effective Banking industry Management. A question made use of to provide link for the fundamental or elements in the model presented in H0₁ states thus:

How satisfied or dissatisfied would you substantiate the idea that Human Capital is significant to effective Banking industry Management?

Table 4.1: Responses frequencies data for H0₁

	Response Frequencies	Response Frequencies in Percentages (%)
Very Satisfied	189	28.00%
Somewhat Satisfied	214	31.70%
Neutral	101	14.96%
Somewhat Dissatisfied	93	13.78%
Very Dissatisfied	78	11.56%
Total	675	100.00%

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.1 displays the response frequencies obtained for the H0₁ question in absolute figures and also expressed in their percentages. The table also discloses the traits of data procured from field survey and shows that 28.00% of total respondents signified very satisfied to the fact that Human Capital is important and critical to instituting effective management of banking institutions. A larger group constituting 31.70% agreed to a considerable extent that Human capital is essential and may relatively be unavoidable to managing banking firms effectively. The positive answer options put together indicate that 59.70% of all respondents are of the opinion that Human capital is a relevant variable. Its relevance emanates from the fact that it plays vital role in effective banking management because of its direct impacts on the bank’s ability to achieve its goals and objectives. The response frequencies expressed in percentages are constructed into a column chart in figure 4.1 to distinctively exhibit their core features.

Figure 4.1: Column chart for H0₁.

Source: Authors’ impression, 2025.

4.1.1 Hypothesis One (H0₁) Estimation

The data analysis tool employed is the PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient model specified in section three. To compute the products or sums of the components of the model in equation 2, table 4.2 is brought to bear.

Table 4.6: Deriving the sums (Σ) of model variables for H0₁

	X	Y	x = X - X̄	y = Y - Ȳ	xy	x ²	y ²
Very Satisfied	5	189	2	54	108	4	2916
Somewhat Satisfied	4	214	1	79	79	1	6241
Neutral	3	101	00	-34	00	00	1156
Somewhat Dissatisfied	2	93	-1	-42	42	1	1764
Very Dissatisfied	1	78	-2	-57	114	4	3249
Total (Σ)	15	675	00	00	343	10	15326

Source: Authors’ computation, 2025.

Mean of Weighted Answer Options; $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$

Mean of Frequency Response Options $\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y}{n} = \frac{675}{5} = 135$

PPMCC or ‘r’ Coefficient $= \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{343}{\sqrt{10 \times 15326}} = \frac{343}{391.48} = 0.8762$

PPMCC or ‘r’ = 0.8762 and
Coefficient of Determination (r²) = (0.8762)² = 0.7677 or 76.77%

4.2 Presentation of Data for H0₂

The relationship subsisting between Structural Capital and effective Banking industry Management was examined with the empirical evaluation and analysis of Hypothesis two (H0₂). The question engaged in capturing the relative association between the variables states thus:

To what extent are you Certain or Uncertain that Structural Capital could be put into use to facilitate effective Banking industry Management?

The response frequency data obtained from field survey to analyze H0₂ are made public in table 4.3 in numeral and also expressed in percentages.

Table 4.3: Responses Frequencies Data for H0₂

	Response Frequencies	Response Frequencies in Percentages (%)
Very Certain	163	24.15%
Somewhat Certain	207	30.67%
Neutral	116	17.18%
Somewhat Uncertain	99	14.67%
Very Uncertain	90	13.33%
Total	675	100.00%

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 4.3 exhibits the response frequencies distribution for H0₂ and disclosed that 24.15% of overall respondents are very certain that Structural Capital could be used to promote effective Banking industry Management. Besides, another segment of respondents with outstanding 30.67% are certain to a high degree that the variable Structural Capital is relevant. Deductions from the foregoing show that 54.82% of respondents expressed positive opinion in affirming that Structural Capital is relevant to formulating policies to boost management effectiveness in the Banking industry. The response data are reproduced in the column chart shown in figure 4.2 to display their precise nature.

Figure 4.2: Column chart for H0₂

Source: Authors’ impression, 2025

4.2.1 Hypothesis H0₂ Estimation

As usual, the model in equation 2 was put into use to compute and manipulate the value of its PPMCC or ‘r’ coefficient for H0₂. To ease computation, the sums of the components making up the variables in the model were derived using table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Deriving the sums (Σ) of model variables for H0₂

	X	Y	x = X - \bar{X}	y = Y - \bar{Y}	xy	x ²	y ²
Very Certain	5	163	2	28	56	4	784
Somewhat Certain	4	207	1	72	72	1	5184
Neutral	3	116	00	-19	00	00	361
Somewhat Uncertain	2	99	-1	-36	36	1	1296
Very Uncertain	1	90	-2	-45	90	4	2025
Total (Σ)	15	675	00	00	254	10	9650

Source: Authors’ computation, 2025.

Mean of Weighted Answer Options; $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$

Mean of Frequency Response Options $\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y}{n} = \frac{675}{5} = 135$

$$PPMCC, 'r' = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{254}{\sqrt{10 \times 9650}} = \frac{254}{310.64} = 0.8177$$

PPMCC) or $r = 0.8177$ and Coefficient of Determination (r^2) = $(0.8177)^2 = 0.6686$ or 66.86%.

4.3 Presentation of Data for H0₃

Hypothesis three (H0₃) explored the association between Relationship Capital and effective management of Banking operations. The question connecting the variables for this hypothesis being reviewed states as below shows:

How contented or discontented would you validate, confirm or certify that applying Relationship Capital could help to augment effective management of banking firms' operations?

The response frequencies elicited from field survey are exhibited in table 4.5 for analysis.

Table 4.5: Response frequency for H0₃

	Response Frequencies in absolute figures	Response Frequencies in Percentages (%)
Very Contented	141	20.89%
Somewhat Contented	236	34.96%
Neutral	103	15.26%
Somewhat Discontented	128	18.96%
Very Discontented	67	9.93%
Total	675	100.00 %

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.5 disclosed distinctively that while 20.89% of total respondents indicate that they are very contented, 34.96% expressed contentment to some degree though positive that Relationship Capital influences effective management of banking industry operations. A fair proportion of the frequencies obtained and constituting 18.96% expressed discontentment. That-notwithstanding, a total of 55.85% are positive that the application or usage of Relationship capital inspires effective banking management. The data highlighted for the frequencies in table 4.5 expressed in percentages are further used to construct the chart in figure 4.3 to clearly exhibit the Response Frequencies data features distinctively.

Figure 4.3: Column chart for H0₃.

Source: Authors' impression, 2025.

4.3.1 Estimation of Hypothesis H0₃

To compute the sum total of the variables as specified in the PPMCC model derived, we utilized table 4.5. On derivation of the totals of the model components, the PPMCC or 'r' coefficient and the Coefficient of Determination (r²) were computed.

Table 4.5: Deriving the sums (Σ) of model variables for H0₃

	X	Y	x = X - \bar{X}	y = Y - \bar{Y}	xy	x ²	y ²
Very Contented	5	141	2	6	12	4	36
Somewhat Contented	4	236	1	101	101	1	10201
Neutral	3	103	0	-32	00	00	1024
Somewhat Discontented	2	128	-1	-7	7	1	49
Very Discontented	1	67	-2	-68	136	4	4624
Total (Σ)	15	675	00	00	256	10	15934

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

Mean of Weighted Answer Options; $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$

Mean of Frequency Response Options $\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum Y}{n} = \frac{675}{5} = 135$

$$\text{PPMCC; } r^{xy} = \frac{\sum xy}{\sqrt{\sum x^2 \sum y^2}} = \frac{256}{\sqrt{10 \times 15934}} = \frac{256}{399.17} = 0.6413$$

PPMCC or 'r' = 0.6413 and
Coefficient of Determination (r²) = (0.6413)² = 0.4113 or 41.13%

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The research model has been estimated for the hypotheses formulated and products for two measuring parameters derived to assist our discussions of research findings. The parameters include:

- i. The Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) or 'r' and
- ii. The Coefficient of Determination (r²) referred to as adjusted R squared.

For ease of understanding the importance and purpose of these statistical parameters, it might be necessary to provide some explanation to their usefulness or rather what they measure. The PPMCC or 'r' coefficient assures us of the extent or degree of linear relationship in existence between two variables and it measures or expresses two entities. While the magnitude signifies the size of the coefficient to indicate how strong and robust or weak and feeble the relationship assumes, the sign attached to the coefficient indicates the direction the relationship tilts, whether it is leaning towards positive side or sloping to the negative side. As earlier stated, when the 'r' coefficient is squared, it generates the Coefficient of Determination (r²). Oaikhenan and Udegbanan (2005), posits that the adjusted R squared is a statistical measures that signifies the proportion and the relative amount of the variance in the explained variable predictable by the explanatory variable(s) in a regression model. We therefore reckon and rely on the computed values of the 'r' and (r²) coefficients to discuss the results and findings exhibited in the hypotheses specified.

Hypothesis one (H0₁) investigated and appraised the relationship and the link between Human Capital component of Intellectual capital and effective Banking industry Management. The estimation of the

hypothesis produced a PPMCC or (r) coefficient standing at 0.8762 and evidencing a strong, positive and linear relationship between Human capital and effective Banking industry management. The positive sign the coefficient carries portend that as Human capital strategies increase, so will banking industry management capabilities will also tend to increase. The high coefficient encourages and demands investing in human capital and appears also to suggest that banking institutions that invest in Human capital which includes training, re-training and development programs are likely to experience improvements and to derive competitive advantage from efficient management. Hypothesis one (H0₁) model also produced its Coefficient of Determination (r²) of 0.7677 or 76.77%. The (r²) coefficient gauges the proportion of variance in effective Banking industry management that is explained by Human capital. The (r²) value of 0.7677 indicates a strong and powerful positive inter-relationship between Human capital and effective Banking industry management. It implies that the model has high predictive power as Human capital variable can explain a significant proportion of the variation in Bank management effectiveness. By considering these facts, it implies that banking firms in Nigeria should develop Human capital strategies to optimize and improve management processes in the Banking industry.

Hypothesis two (H0₂) explored the association existing between Structural Capital, an inherent element of Intellectual Capital and effective Banking industry Management. The end product of the empirically estimated H0₂ revealed an 'r' coefficient of 0.8177 indicating a strong positive linear and undeviating association between Structural capital and effective Bank management. That the coefficient is positive implies that as the acquisition of structural capital increases, it drives effectiveness of management processes in the banking industry which will also increase. It implies and suggests that banks that invest on structural capital, prioritize infrastructural development and focus on process improvement including streamlining operations, reducing cost and enhancing clients experience are likely to have competitive edge being able to effectively manage their resources. The accompanying Coefficient of Determination (r²) for H0₂ showed 0.6686 signifying that approximately 66.86% of the variation in effective Banking industry management can be explained by Structural capital. An (r²) coefficient of 0.6686 suggests a somewhat moderate to strong and positive relationship between Structural capital and effective Banking industry management. The displayed coefficient means that the model exhibits a middling and still adequate predictive power, as it can explain a fairly relevant proportion of variation in banking industry management. The coefficient suggests that banks that invest in Structural capital such as information technology, knowledge management systems and physical infrastructures are likely to see significant advancement in Bank management.

Hypothesis three (H0₃) evaluated the relation subsisting between Relationship Capital, an integral and fundamental element of Intellectual Capital and effective Banking industry Management. The computed PPMCC or 'r' for H0₃ amounted to 0.6413 and this signifies a moderate to strong positive linear relationship existing between Relationship Capital and effective Banking industry Management. The positive sign of correlation coefficient being interpreted means that as the bank enhances or improves on its Relationship capital; there will be a corresponding enhancement of banking industry management. Impliedly, it suggests that a banking firm that builds strong, viable and workable relationships with clients and stakeholders and develop strong partnerships with other financial institutions, financial technology companies and technology providers could hopefully enhance their management processes efficiently. H0₃ produced an adjusted (r²) of 0.4113 which suggests that approximately 41.13% of the variation in effective Banking industry management can be explained by Relationship capital. The R-squared coefficient of 0.4113 or 41.13% indicates a moderate positive relationship between Relationship capital and effective Banking industry management. The coefficient could be said to have a moderately predictive power as it can explain only a limited proportion of the variance in effective banking management. Overall, it slightly passed the test of relevance and may have exerted very moderate influence in boosting efficient Banking industry management.

5.1 CONCLUSION

Overall, the results of the three models of hypotheses estimated displayed some similarities. All the computed values of PPMCC or 'r' exhibited positive signs meaning that the three proxies of Intellectual Capital, namely: Human, Structural and Relationship capitals have a direct relationship with effective Banking industry management. The coefficients revealed moderate to high values denoting that they are significant and have the ability to leverage effective banking industry management. In particular, the coefficients of H_{01} showed extreme high value of PPMCC or 'r' at 0.8762 signifying a near perfect relationship and also exhibited high value of (r^2). The 'r' and (r^2) coefficients of H_{02} equally displayed high values attesting to significant influence on effective banking industry management. However, the 'r' and (r^2) coefficients for H_{03} exhibited moderate to high values which attests to a somewhat average influence on banking management. Based on the forgoing analysis and discussions we conclude that Intellectual Capital as per the influences of its proxies can be counted relevant to formulating policies to boost and augment effective Banking industry management in Nigeria.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Inferences drawn from the three null hypotheses formulated, estimated and analyzed suggest that the concept and theory of Intellectual capital is an essential prerequisite for effective banking industry management. We are therefore recommending that banking institutions should invest on Human, Structural and Relationship capital programs such as employee training and re-training, information technology, physical infrastructures, knowledge management systems, and build strong and winning relationships with partners, stakeholders and customers so as to improve on Banking industry management.

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Reference

- Adegbayibi A. T (2021), Intellectual Capital and firm performance of listed firms in Nigeria: Moderating Role of Corporate Governance. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis* ·Volume 10, (1), pp. 1-12
- Aguirre P.A. U and Alecchi B.E.A (2023), Impact of Intellectual Capital on organizational Performance through intrinsic motivation in higher education institutions; *Cogent Business and Management*. 10(1) 1-21
- Banyai T, Landschuter C. and Banyai A (2018), Markov-chain simulation-based analysis of human resource structure: how Staffing deployment and and stage affect sustainable human resource strategy. *Sustainability*. 10(3), 36 - 92
- Becker G. S. [2001]. *Talking Human Capital with Gary S. Becker Learning in the New Economy*. Spring (at www.linezine.com). Cited in Knights D and Wilmoth H (2007)
- Boone (Jr) H.N. and Boone D.A. (2012) *Analyzing Likert Data*; Retrieved from: <http://www.joe.org/joe/2012april/tt2.php>.
- Chaabane (2021), The impact of the intellectual Capital components on firm's performance in emerging markets. *Risk Governance and control> Financial Markets and Institutions*, 11(2) 8 - 17
- Chen J (2021), Intellectual Capital: Definition, Types, Measurement, Importance. Retrieved from: https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/intellectual_capital.asp
- Creswell J. W. (2005). *Educational Research, Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc.

- Duho K. C and Agomor P.E (2021), Intellectual Capital and Performance among listed non-financial firms in West Africa. *Datating Working Paper Series N WP2021-03-02*. Retrieved from: <http://ssrn.com/abstract>
- ExxonMobil (2014), *ExxonMobil Summary Annual Report*. Retrieved from: <https://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/>
- Habib M. (2018), Are Human Capital, intellectual Property Rights and Research and Development Expenditures Really important to total factor productivity. An Empirical Analysis; *International Journal of Social Economics*, 34(5), 21-43
- Hanady B, Sinan S. A, Enas A and Amneh A (2022), The effect of intellectual capital on firm performance: the mediating role of family management; *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, vol. 13, issue 5, 845-863
- Marr, B., Schiuma, G., and Neely, A. (2004). The dynamics of value Creation—Mapping Your Intellectual Performance Drivers. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 5, 312-325.
- Nasar, S. (2018). Impact of intellectual capital on firm performance of the Turkish real estate companies before and after the crisis. *European Scientific Journal*, 14(1), 45-60
- Oaikhenan and Udegbunan (2004), *Modern Statistics for Economics and Business*, Benin City; H. Henans Publishers
- Payam, M., & Mohammad, A. (2013). The effects of intellectual capital on economic value added in Malaysians companies. *Current Research Journal of Economic Theory*, 5(2), 20-24.
- Sauro J. (2011) *How to interpret survey responses: 5 techniques*. Retrieved from: <http://www.measuringu.com/blog/interpret-responses>.
- VanZyl C. R (2005), Structural Capital management creates sustainable Competitiveness and Prolonged first-mover advantage. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/307793849_Structural_capital_management_creates_sustainable_competitiveness_and_pr
- Wronski L. (2018), *Let's agree NOT to use agree/disagree questions*. Retrieved from: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/curiosity/lets-agree-not-use->
- Yusoff W. F and Alhaji I.A (2012), Corporate Governance and firm performance of listed companies in Malaysia. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291035589_